

EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF GUIDANCE AND COUNSELLING SERVICES: A PANACEA FOR REINVENTING THE NIGERIA EDUCATION FOR GLOBAL COMPETITIVENESS

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ABSTRACT

RESEARCH ARTICLE

The roles of guidance and counselling service in reinventing the Nigeria's education for global competitiveness cannot be measured. This paper has surveyed the panacea to reinventing the Nigeria's education for global competitiveness. It has been observed that effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in schools is an enormous task that requires concerted effort by all educational stakeholders. Stakeholders therefore should totally accept to do their best, be focused and committed to follow the principles and ethics of the profession, have mutual trust and respect for each other as a team in their working relationship. We wish to conclude by remarking that, driving the Nigeria's education for global competition demands educational excellence. In order for the Nigerian education system to reach the level of excellence required full and effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in the school system, as it forms the integral parts of academic excellence.

KEYWORDS: Guidance and Counselling, Effective Implementation, Panacea for Reinventing the Nigeria's Education

INTRODUCTION

Education is as old as human existence on earth. Upon all the primary human life survival tools and skills, education stands out as the most singular powerful instrument of life, sharpening and retooling all the others, along the years. Education today still remains a global matter in all the nations, because of the intellectual power it produces which governs all aspect of life and sustainable development. Since 1960 when Nigeria gained political independence, the country, has had governments with low capacity for people-driven and inclusive development programming options. In many of these governments, decisions on the type, location and timing of a development intervention was a function of the whims and caprices of policy makers who hardly understood the interface between development and conflict, especially in the heterogeneous society of Nigeria. Numerous development projects were poorly conceived and as a consequence, impacted negatively on the people. Needless to

say that, development challenges bordering on issues of human rights, academic, political and economic inclusion were part of the causal factors of the Nigerian civil war.

Education is means by which citizens are equipped with the necessary attitudes knowledge and skills that will enable them contribute meaningfully to national as well as human development. Thus every nation of the world has recognized and accepted education as the springboard of societal development. For developing nations in particular education remains a potent factor for eradicating poverty and changing the misfortune of under development. There is usually a high correlation between the overall level of development of any given society and her system of education. In fact a high rate of development is a product of a well-organized, managed and supervised educational system. However, a badly managed, crisis ridden and highly disorganized system of education portends grave consequences on the developmental efforts of any nation.

Okpala, (2014) lamented that the history of inadequate planning capacity in Nigeria has had destabilizing effects on development at the micro (individual), meso (community), and macro (country) levels. In particular, the politics of the exploitation of oil, the control and appropriation of the huge, revenues accruable to this sector, and the political economy of systemic conuptions have remained the mainstay of the centrifugal forces that sustain conflict in the context of development. Development and conflict counts as part of and more expensive to make them become good learners later in their lives.

In Nigeria there were quite a number of education policies that were expected to ensure the growth and personal development of the citizen in all areas, which would in turn translate to national development. Many of these policies were laudable. However, a number of missteps have often aborted goal fulfillment in the education sector. The malaise that first bedeviled the education system according the Belo-Osagie and Olugbamila (2010) were:

- a. Faults in policy implememation; and b. Frequent changes in government especially during the military rule.
- b. These twin problems invariably led to lack of continuation of programmes by successive administrations. More worrisome is that the progress made in various areas of the education sector within the five decades of independence were not consolidated, resulting into highs and lows — the lows representing years of neglect, misappropriation of funds and poor policy implementation which have undermined the investments made in various aspects of the education sector.

Right from the onset, Nigeria's philosophy of education as aptly enunciated in the National Policy on Education (2004) was based on:

- a. The development of the individual into a sound and effective citizen.
- b. The full integration of the individual into the community, and
- c. The provision or equal access to educational opportunities for all citizens of the country at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels both inside and outside the formal school system.

The provision of counselling services to students is an important instrument for the management of social processes and testifies to the strengthening humanistic trends in our society.

Guidance

According to Agi (2006). 'guidance is a process of helping an individual understands himself and the world.- She also sees guidance as a programme of services to individual student based upon the needs of each student and understanding of his immediate environment, the influences of the factors on the student and the unique feature of each school. Similarly. Agi (2006) cited Zeran and

Riccio (1962) that guidance is a process, developmental in nature by which an individual is assisted to understand, accept and utilize his abilities, aptitudes, interests and attitudinal patterns in relations to his aspiration. Ajoku (2009) pointed out that a good guidance policy should be educative, curative, futuristic as well as preventive. Guidance services deals with problems that have arisen from the developmental stages of individual students and prevent these major problems (educational, vocational and socio-psychological), from surfacing because "an ounce of prevention is worth a pound of cure" (Ajoku. 2009).

Remalingam (2006) in his view stated that guidance is a professional assistance provided to an individual with aid of interviews and tests for maximizing the satisfaction of the individual whereas Uzoeshi (2005) affirmed that guidance is a program designed to help an individual understand himself, his environment in relation to his abilities and limitations.

Counselling

Counselling is defined by Uzoelti (2005) as a process in which an individual who is helpless (client) is assisted by uninvolved individual (Counsellor) to overcome his helplessness through information interaction, decision-making and conducive environment. In the same vein, Olayinka (1978) in Unachukwu (1989) defined Counselling as a process in which one person helps another in a one-to-one and a face-to- face encounter. 'Assessing the above definitions, we will assert that counselling is a process whereby a professionally trained personnel (counsellor) renders assistance to individual or, group of individuals (clients) who have problems (that could be educational, vocational or psychological) to understand and overcome these problems or needs effortlessly. The counsellor serves as a coach focusing on the potentials of the client to help him understand himself.

Guidance and Counselling Services for Global Competitiveness

Changing societal and family values, traditions as well as disintegrated community; form the bases for psychological and social issues affecting students in institutions of learning (Wambu & Fisher, 2015). Mapfumo and Nkoma, (2013) noted that students experience immense socio-economic and psychological pressures in today's world, which disturb their learning process. These negative societal trends have underscored the increasing demand for the services of professional teacher counsellors to provide a comprehensive Guidance and Counselling Programme in secondary schools to effectively address the needs of students. In response to this demand, Guidance and Counselling programme was implemented in the United States and it became prominent in American schools after the World War I (Corsini, 1987). In support, Taylor (1971) states that school counselling was implemented in British schools in reaction to the changes in society, in family life and in schools which created conditions where greater attention to individual needs was necessary.

In Africa, the concept of Guidance and Counselling although relatively new in educational systems, has been embraced by most movement (UNESCO), 2001). Considerable progress has been made setting up administrative structures for the provision of Guidance and

Counselling services in educational institutions to enhance personal, educational and vocational development of the students. Therefore Guidance and Counselling has been conceptualized as a programme of activities which has provided African countries with the gateway out of the existing numerous problems in the present age of complex scientific and technological development (Okobiah & Okorodudu, 2004). Guidance and Counselling was formally implemented in Kenyan institutions of learning in 1971 to help students deal with emotional, psychological, educational, vocational and social problems that confront them in their daily lives (Wango, 2007). The implementation of Guidance Counselling programme was based on a number of recommendations and guidelines in various Education Commissions Reports, National Development Plans and Government Sessional Papers (MOEST, 2004).

According to Eyo, Joshua and Esuong (2010) guidance and counselling programmes for secondary school students are designed to address the physical, emotional, social, vocational and academic difficulties of adolescent students. In Kenya, the purpose of guidance and counselling programme as stipulated in the Ministry of Education Handbook on Guidance and Counselling (Republic of Kenya, 2007) is to help the student meet a great variety of needs ranging from psychological and sociological to academic adjustment. Guidance and Counselling being an important part of the total programme of instruction should therefore be provided in accordance with the state laws and regulations and the Ministry of Education policies and regulation (Wango, 2007).

Teacher counsellors are expected to develop Guidance and Counselling programmes in schools that will assist in developing all rounded individuals. To achieve this, the programme should target all areas of guidance and counselling which according to MOEST, (2004) include personal and social, vocational, health and educational guidance and counselling among others. Despite all the expectations according to ASCA (2005), countries vary on how Guidance and Counselling programme is being implemented. While Guidance and Counselling is an easily accessible service in many developed countries, its benefits are not yet adequately exploited in developing and third world countries (Hiebert & Bezanson, 2002). In some countries the provision of G&C services is considered a luxury that should only be made available largely to choice of subjects (Gysber & Henderson. 200). Harel and Erhard (2005) noted that school counselling role varied due to; the school counselor's preference, school level and school principal expectations. In other cases like Korea, India, Zambia, Nigeria and Kenya, Guidance Counselling is provided by classroom teachers, who either have such duties added to their usual teaching load or teach only limited loads that also includes counselling (ASCA, 2005). In Nigeria, many secondary schools counsellors function as career masters or mistresses and they also have teaching responsibilities that take time away from their counselling roles.

Roles of Guidance and Counselling in Reinventing the Nigeria's Education for Global Competitiveness

Driving the Nigeria's education for global competition demands educational excellence. In order for the Nigerian education system to reach the level of excellence required full implementation of guidance and counselling services in the school system, as it forms the integral parts of academic excellence.

In any school setting the roles of the guidance counsellor include the following:-

- Taking charge of establishing school guidance programme.
- Coordinating the guidance programme in schools
- Define objectives of the school guidance programme for the benefit of the principals, teachers, parents and the students.
- Helping to disseminate career information of the students
- Playing major role in the identification of the guidance needs of the students.
- Supervising the building and maintenance of students' cumulative records in schools
- Providing relevant data for the placement of students in the transition from junior to senior secondary schools.
- Assisting parents in relating student's interest, attitudes and abilities to current future educational, occupational opportunities and requirement.
- Providing counselling service to the students regarding their educational, vocational and personal social concern.
- Assisting students and parents to understand procedures for applying to higher institutions and for financing student's education.
- Functioning as a resource person to teach in exhibited classroom.

Majority of the students in our Nigeria's schools lack a sense of direction, a sense of purpose and a sense of fulfillment and indulge in destructive activities, which lead to social damage and loss. Adequate guidance and counselling facilities is the only answer to help and guide the youth to worthwhile channels and help them realize the goals of optimum academic, personal and social development, contemporary society needs and trends. Problems and needs in society are nothing new, but today they seem to be proliferating at an unprecedented rate. The unique problems in the changing family, cities in upheaval, conflicts in values, attitudes and moral, the new cynicism about politics, economic factors, the changing role of work, new pressure and demands on school, and problems of the youth, all points out the need for the counselling services. Guidance and counselling have a challenging role to play in every developing economy, much more so if it is a labour surplus onr.

However, this paper is advocating that if we as a nation must succeed in the global competition, there is an urgent need to implement effective guidance and counselling services in our educational system. Hence, it was observed that:

- Counselling deals with wellness, personal growth, career, education and empowerment concerns. In other words, counsellors work in areas that involve a plethora of issues including those that are personal and those that are interpersonal. These areas include concerns related to finding meaning, adjustment, and fulfillment in mental and physical health and the achievement of goals in such settings as work and school. Counselors are concerned with social justice and advocate for the oppressed and powerless as a part of the process.

- Counselling is conducted with persons individually, in groups, and in families. Clients seen by counsellors live and work in a wide variety of settings. Their problems may require short-term or long-term interventions that focus on just one person or with multiple individuals who are related or not related to each other.
- Counselling is diverse and multicultural. Counsellors see clients with varied cultural backgrounds. Those from minority and majority cultures are helped in a variety of ways depending on their needs, which may include addressing larger societal issues such as discrimination or prejudice.
- Counselling is a dynamic process. Counsellors not only focus on their clients' goals, they help clients accomplish them. This dynamic process comes through using a variety of theories and methods.

Furthermore, counselling is an all-encompassing activities meant to ensure proper and perfect development, adjustment and stability of an individual with the aim of total understanding of self, environment and opportunities and in the light of these make decisions that are paramount in achieving stated goals.

Being an integral part of guidance, it is perceived that counselling basically provides the following services:

- Educational Counselling: This involves measures aimed at facilitating learning and high achievement. According to Olayinka (1999), educational counselling are activities designed to assist all categories of learners (from primary to tertiary level). Educational counselling includes activities such as entering appropriate educational programmes, subject selection, effective study habit, strategies for minimizing examination anxiety and success in examination. For university students it includes choice of course of study, choice of electives, overcoming academic stress, change of course of study or faculty, developing appropriate reading habits and skills, among others. Osarenren (2011) noted that educational counselling focuses on issues pertaining to academic success and furtherance of education. It aims at helping clients to realise their educational goals.
- Career/Vocational Counselling: This provides information about conditions of work, the existing opportunity in the world of work. It helps individual to have clearer understanding of his/her ability, interest, disposition in relation to the world of work and its demands. It also exposes the client to the vocation he can choose from considering his ability', aptitudes, interest and personality. Osarenren (2011) noted that through vocational counselling students are enlightened about job requirements, duration of training, the emoluments, job prospects and hazards.
- Personal/Social Counselling: This is concerned with counselling individuals with personal problems such as low self-esteem, negative self-concept and lack of self-understanding. It also deals with social problems such as emotional disturbances, sexual malfunctioning, family, financial and other socially induced problems. Personal/Social Counselling is a process whereby an individual is made to understand how his emotional, intellectual and motivational forces affect his relationship with others and his personal adjustment in the pursuit and attainment of his life goals. According to Aluede (2017), school counsellors can assist students on management of emotional abuse by equipping them with skills in self-advocacy and assertiveness. He stressed that students who possessed self-advocacy skills are more motivated to attend

schools and are capable of making concrete decisions that directly affect their success in life.

- **Financial counselling:** This is a counselling service through which financial guide is provided to students who want to effectively manage their income and assets. It assists clients to judiciously utilise their income, engage in savings and avoid bankruptcy. Through financial counselling, indigent students are assisted to benefit from loans, scholarships and awards. Financial counselling also offers basic education on financial management and accountability.
- **Health counselling:** This involves provision of assistance to clients who have concerns about their health. It focuses on promotion of good physical and mental conditions and freedom from diseases. Counsellors, therefore create awareness on causes, manifestations and prevention of diseases. They also encourage clients to live a healthy life.
- **Marriage counselling:** Marriage counselling involves preparation of client for conjugal relationships and promotion of marital satisfaction. It comprises provision of assistance on mate selection, handling of marital challenges and sustenance of family life values. All these skills are needed by students in order to become successful adults.
- **Religious counselling:** Spirituality and religion have therapeutic value in counselling. Through religious counselling, counsellors are able to assist clients to practise their religions peacefully, respect the religious beliefs of others and use religion for the development of the society. With appropriate religious counselling, religious conflicts and extreme religious practices could be adequately controlled.

Challenges Facing the Effective Implementation of Guidance and Counselling Services

It is observed that the common, problem in developing countries is their need for human resources and expertise. In Nigeria, one begins to question if counselling services are really planned and implemented properly in schools. Despite the noble objectives of the Federal Government of Nigeria, counselling in Nigeria has not been able to attain the expected standard when compared with professions such as medicine, law, engineering, pharmacy among others (Yahaya, 2017). Some of the factors responsible for the low standard of counselling practice in Nigeria include:

1. **Inconsistent government policies:** The Federal Government of Nigeria seems to recognize the importance of counselling, however, not much has been done to uplift the standard of the profession. For instance, many schools in Nigeria have no guidance counsellors and where they exist, they are made to teach or combine teaching with counselling. According to Idowu (2001), guidance and counselling only features in six lines subsumed in several paragraphs of an omnibus section termed “Educational Services” in the National Policy on Education rather than having a section of its own. Also, guidance and counselling has no independent unit in the Federal Ministry of Education, just as in State Ministries of Education in Nigeria. This untoward attitude on the part of government has led to the seeming lack of clarity of role.

2. **Inadequate funding:** Funding is a major source or challenge. Omoegun (2012) noted that in most Nigerian schools, funds are inadequately provided for guidance and counselling programmes. According to her, the inadequacy can be attributed to lack of provision of funds by government for the running of the programme in schools. Private organisations have also shown little or no interest in terms of financial support for the running of effective guidance and counselling programme. The situation seems to persist despite the dire need for counselling in Nigerian schools.
3. **Inadequate facilities:** Many schools lack adequate facilities to provide effective counselling services. For example, many schools lack adequate office accommodation, storage facilities (e.g file cabinets, computer units and shelves), psychological tests and non-test devices, Communication gadgets and transport facilities; hence they are unable to make such available to school counsellors.
4. **Inadequate number of qualified counsellors in schools:** The global standard regarding the number of students per counsellor is two hundred and fifty (American Counselling Association, 2005). However, Yahaya (2017) lamented that in most educational institutions in Nigeria, there are no qualified counsellors at all and where they exist, the counsellor-students ratio is abnormally lopsided in the face of the size of students.
5. **Cultural barriers:** Cultural barriers take the forms of differences in language, belief systems, religion and cultural background. For instance, some students find it difficult to discuss their concerns with school counsellors whom they regard as "strangers" from different religious or cultural background. Also many secondary school students cannot communicate effectively in English language and thus they find it difficult to discuss their concerns school counsellors. Ipaye (2001) noted that some Nigerians view counselling as an invasion of individual privacy. Consequently, this group of people always attempt to frustrate rather than support guidance programmes in schools. Similarly, Ipaye (2003) observed that in the African society, authority is patrilineal and thus every member of the family is expected to take directives from and respect, the authority of the father. As a result of this, many students find it difficult to decide on issues without references to their fathers or parents.
6. **Ignorance:** Due to inadequate information, many organizations that require the services of counsellors in Nigeria do not appreciate the need for their services and thus failed to employ them in their organizations. Such organizations include hospitals, prisons, police, military, welfare centers, banks, courts of law and marriage registries. Omoegun (2012) noted that the awareness of the usefulness of counselling to human development is still limited in Nigeria and that even in the school setting; effective guidance and counseling programmes have not emerged on a large scale.
7. **Negative attitude of school administrators and other school personnel:** Many school personnel, especially the administrators, display a negative attitude to counselling practitioners and this may be attributed to conservatism or resistance to change and innovation in education. Consequently, school counsellors are usually denied the financial and moral supports required for efficient job performance. For instance, some school administrators direct school counsellors to teach on a full-time basis rather than encourage them to engage in their professional responsibility, which is counselling. This contravenes the guidelines of the National Council on Education (NCE) Task Force of 1988, which states that school counsellors should be employed on a full-time basis.

8. Negative attitude of counselling practitioners: Some counsellors are sources of concern to the counselling profession. This group of counsellors displays a lackadaisical attitude to their jobs and to their profession. Some engage in other businesses such as selling of wares in their places of work. By these acts, they display inadequate job commitment, which negatively influences their productivity and work ethics. Omoegun (2012) noted that one of the major problems in the practice of guidance and counselling in Nigeria is that, which is inherent in the counsellors. According to her, counsellors are the source of their problems by not proving their worth to convince the people that they have essential services to offer.
9. Lack of a professional board: According to Rupande and Tapfumaneyi (2013), professional counselling in Africa is not being viewed as authentic and systematic. In Nigeria, there is no professional counselling board. As a result, counselling services are being offered without any kind of quality control measure in place. The implication is that the profession is still in its infancy, especially when compared with the standard practice in the Western world. Up till date, professional associations of counsellors are still struggling to professionalize counselling in Nigeria. The consequence is that unqualified individuals claim to have the skills and competence of qualified counsellors.
10. Over-generalization: Rupande and Taplumancyi (2013) noted that counsellor education programmes in Africa are at times too generalised and lack focus in terms of specialisation. In spite of the diverse fields of counselling, all aspects are lumped together in the process of training counsellors. In the United States of America for example, one can earn specialised degrees such as Master's degree in School Counselling, Master's degree in Mental Health Counselling or Master's degree in Rehabilitation Counselling. It is therefore important that the National Universities Commission and other similar bodies encourage universities to narrow their focus to specific counselling fields in order to give counselling the needed specialised appeal and enhance professional practice in Nigeria.

Suggestions/Way Forward for Effective Implementation of Guidance and Counselling Services in Nigeria's Education for Global Competitiveness

The implementation of Guidance and Counselling services requires adequate funding which is the key factor for proper implementation of the guidance services, the areas that should be funded are training of human resources (Counselors) through scholarship scheme at Bachelor and Master's level.

The Federal and State Ministries should play the leadership role of policy formulation and implementation. Consequently in the year 1988, the Federal Ministry of Education at the meeting of the National Council on Education setup the following policy guidelines for states to implement concerning counseling services in Nigerian schools.

1. States should intensify training programmers to produce enough guidance counselors for all post primary institutions within the state.
2. Train career masters/mistresses using the criteria spelt out in the taskforce report on guidance and counselling interim measure before the production of adequate qualified guidance counselors.

3. States are to use their scholarship schemes in training counselors at Bachelor and Master of Education levels.
4. Federal Government would also train more counselors at Masters Level through her yearly scholarship programmed.
5. All qualified counselors should be redeployed to function as lit) time counselors in schools and not used as teachers of subjects.
6. States should have counseling units/sections in the Ministries of Education headed by a trained qualified counselor.
7. States should create separate budgetary allocation for implementing counselling services and programme, in all levels of operation namely (Ministry, Zonal and School levels).
8. The implementation of guidance and counseling services in the state should he supervised, monitored and evaluated on regular basis. These polices are yet to be adequately implemented.

This paper suggests that the states should aspire at having at least one counsellor per school, also, the state should develop "model/standard counseling centre" with modem equipment and infrastructure in the state capital for schools in the state to copy or emulate. This "model counseling centre" should carry out major guidance services that will act as a basic pattern/guide to all other schools in the state. The Federal Government is to assume the leadership role of policy formulation and the State Government of setting up of one "model Guidance and Counselling centre" in her capital city of all schools in the state to use as guide.

The school guidance committee should be perhaps made up of the following members;

1. The principal, who should be the chairman
2. The Counsellor, who should be the Secretary
3. The HOD's for Science, Arts, Commerce and Technical vocational subject's members.
4. Senior House Master/Mistress -Member
5. Physical Education Teacher - Member
6. The School Medical Personnel/Nurse- Member
7. Representative of the Parents Teachers Association (PTA) and student's representative when necessary — members.

The role of the guidance committee will be to assist each school in planning, organizing and mapping out strategies for effective implementation of guidance programs in their schools. They will also assist the school on issues relating to students values, behavior reports, and procurement of physical facilities support, encouraging smooth and cordial relationship between the counsellor and the school personnel and parents, in the full implementation of the guidance and counseling services and programme delivery for global competitiveness.

Furthermore, Mogbo, Obumneke-Okeke & Anyachebelu (2011) suggested that the following important services should be offered in every schools from primary to tertiary level in Niger and Anambra state schools:

1. Orientation service/programme for new students
2. Study skills examination phobia/anxiety skills
3. Decision making, healthy interrelationship skills particularly between boys and girls
4. Remedial and referral guidance
5. Vocational and occupational information guidance programmes
6. Placement service (counsel on choice of subjects, class and course selection programmers).
7. Stress management and management of time and resources programs)
8. Use of library, textbooks, internet search programmes
9. Local research into educational, vocational and personal social problems, concerns of students in schools at all levels.

Organizing seminars, talks, workshops, conferences at least annually, this will help stakeholders to get adequate information for proper implementation of guidance and counselling services in all schools in the state. Also support and encouragement of counsellors to do their best, in implementing the programme.

Conclusion

This paper has surveyed the panacea to reinventing the Nigeria's education for global competitiveness. It has been observed that effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in schools is an enormous task that requires concerted effort by all educational stakeholders. Stakeholders therefore should totally accept to do their best, be focused and committed to follow the principle and ethics of the profession, have mutual trust and respect for each other as a team in their working relationship. We wish to conclude by remarking that, driving the Nigeria's education for global competition demands educational excellence. In order for the Nigerian education system to reach the level of excellence required full and effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in the school system, as it forms the integral parts of academic excellence.

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